

Who does not use urban green spaces and why? Insights from a comparative study of thirty-three European countries

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Study based on statistically representative samples from 33 European countries.
- Older people are less likely to use UGS, compared to other age groups.
- Those who have higher education levels are less likely to use UGS.
- Respondents with children are more unlikely than others to use UGS.
- Countries can be meaningfully clustered with regard to the reasons for not using UGS.

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ABSTRACT

There is a large body of research on the benefits green spaces offer city dwellers and how people use urban green spaces (UGS). However, there is much less information on how many people do not use UGS, who these people are, and why they resign from going there. This paper focuses on understanding reasons that restrict the use of UGS and draws the socio-economic and demographic profile of UGS non-users. For this purpose, we surveyed $N = 10,391$ respondents from 33 European countries (statistically representative at the country level). Results show that about 10% of the respondents do not use UGS. However, the share of non-users differs between countries from 2% (Turkey) to 25% (United Kingdom). Results reveal statistically significant differences between those who do not use and those who use UGS across age, education level, and residential location, demonstrating the importance of considering the needs of different groups of people when designing, planning and managing UGS. Lack of time and interest, and long distance from where people live are key limiting factors. The dominant reasons for not using UGS enable us to group the countries using the hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis. With this study, we contribute to the knowledge of personal barriers that prevent UGS use and, in particular, connect the different reasons for not using UGS with the socio-economic groups typically listed as deprived when it comes to UGS provision.

1. Introduction

Urban green spaces (UGS) provide positive mental and physical health benefits to city dwellers (Akpınar, 2016; McCormack et al., 2010; Schipperijn et al., 2010; World Health Organisation, 2016; Zhang et al., 2022). Therefore, increasing the use of UGS is given a lot of attention in health policy agendas (European Commission, 2020; Schipperijn et al., 2010). UGS provide multiple other ecosystem services, many of which

are only available to those who physically enter these spaces (Zwierchowska et al., 2018), such as physical and experiential, as well as intellectual and representative interactions with the natural environment.

To achieve Sustainable Development Goal 11, “Sustainable Cities and Communities”, and ensure “universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces” (UN General Assembly, 2015), researchers and planners consider UGS availability, accessibility, and attractiveness as key factors that may increase the number of people

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visiting UGS (Biernacka et al., 2020). Little is known about why citizens do not use UGS (Boyd et al., 2018; Haase et al., 2021; Hitchings, 2013). Literature shows that some social groups tend to spend little or no time in UGS and are thus potentially excluded or at least partially excluded from the benefits they provide. Most notably, infrequent users or non-users of UGS include immigrants (Buijs et al., 2009; Peters et al., 2010; Sayan & Kalisch, 2018), people experiencing homelessness (Dooling, 2009; Evangelista, 2019; Koprowska et al., 2020), those of lower socio-economic status (Boyd et al., 2018), older people with limited mobility (Sugiyama et al., 2009), and young girls (Lloyd et al., 2008). Meanwhile, individuals in these groups might benefit the most from increased exposure to UGS, for example, through the positive aspect on their health and well-being, which is overall lower for the groups mentioned above (Mitchell & Popham, 2008).

Some studies show that the abovementioned socio-economic and cultural factors might be predictive of the reasons people give for not using UGS. For example, “lack of interest” is one of the most commonly mentioned justifications provided by those living in deprived areas in England (Boyd et al., 2018). Also, long distance from an individual’s home to UGS is often reported as a fundamental reason for not using UGS (Akpınar, 2016; Björk et al., 2008; Giles-Corti et al., 2005; Nielsen & Hansen, 2007; Schipperijn et al., 2010). Indeed, there is strong evidence that issues of proximity from where people live or work to natural environments are usually most problematic for those with lower income who cannot afford travel costs (Aspinall et al., 2010; McCormack et al., 2010). Meanwhile, issues of physical access may overlap with safety concerns, such as fear of crime, fear of unwanted verbal, visual and/or physical behaviours (Morris et al., 2011; Skår, 2010), and fear of falling (Sugiyama et al., 2009).

While most studies, surveys and inventories focus on how people use UGS, at the level of the city (Schindler et al., 2022), region or country (Natural England, 2020), few studies investigated the non-users, particularly at a pan-European level.

Our study aims to present a comprehensive picture of the most common reasons for not using UGS in 33 European countries. The main research questions addressed in this article are: (1) Who are the people who do not visit UGS? (2) Why do they not use UGS? And (3) to what extent do European countries differ in terms of the main reasons for the non-use of UGS?

We limited our understanding of UGS to urban parks and urban and peri-urban forests (Salbitano et al., 2016), while by UGS use we mean physical visits, i.e., direct use, although we acknowledge that people may benefit from UGS in many other ways, even without entering them (e.g., benefitting from microclimate regulation or noise mitigation). However, one of the most obvious and consciously used benefits can be associated with one’s presence in UGS which involves direct contact with nature.

We paid special attention to studying the following socio-economically vulnerable groups: older people, women, those with lower education and income, those with children, and immigrants. This selection was motivated by the fact that – as indicated above – these groups typically enjoy worse UGS provision and hence fewer opportunities to benefit from the different benefits that they offer (Biernacka et al., 2022). The present study provides insights into a better understanding of the reasons for which people do not use UGS and – consequently – into whether and how UGS use could be increased to maximize the broader public benefits (Boyd et al., 2018; Dallimer et al., 2014).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Social survey data

The data for this article were collected between March and July 2021 through an online survey with closed questions conducted in 33 European countries within the Sino-European research project CLEARING HOUSE funded by the Horizon 2020 programme (for more information

on the project, visit <https://clearinghouseproject.eu/>). The aim of the project is to provide and exchange knowledge on the use of urban forests (and other tree-based ecosystems) as providers of nature-based solutions. The survey was designed by researchers at the European Forest Institute in Bonn, Germany, in cooperation with the University of Lodz, Poland, and several other academic partner institutions in Europe and China.

The survey covered different aspects of people’s use or non-use of UGS (associated explicitly with forests and parks) and perceptions of the services and disservices provided by urban forests. The questionnaire comprised seven thematic blocks with 37 questions in total.

The survey was translated into the official languages of the covered countries. The translations were conducted by native speakers who were part of the research consortium or external researchers working in urban forestry. Before approval of any language version, all translations were tested and amended.

For this study, we used selected thematic blocks only. The sections of the questionnaire used to collect data for this study are listed in the [Electronic Supplementary Material Table 1](#). In this study, we focus on those who do not use UGS, i.e., those who answered “I do not go to a forest/park at all” in response to the question “what do you visit most frequently (forest, city forest, park)” – along with the underlying reasons and the socio-economic data for the non-using respondents. The reasons for not using UGS were listed in a closed question with 15 predefined responses (Fig. 1). Respondents’ socio-economic data included gender, age, place of residence, education, having children in a household, citizenship, and income.

2.2. Sampling procedure

The data collection was administered by an external market research company, with direct access to online survey panels in 33 European countries and indirect access to additional countries through their partners. A full sample, from which we extracted UGS non-users, was randomly selected from a network panel consisting of close to 2 million members and used as a sampling frame. This sampling frame covered geographical, social, gender and age distribution of inhabitants across countries – the individual’s features that may translate into different preferences regarding the use of UGS. The panel members were recruited through a diversified multi-sourcing process. To avoid bias, different methods were used in the panel-building process, including partnerships, public relations, public announcements, panel members’ referral programmes and emailing. The panel members were recruited exclusively using permission-based techniques. As a result, the sampling frame for each country had approximately the same distribution of social, age and gender groups as in the population.

Respondents were drawn from the panel members in each country. The proportion of the national distributions per characteristic for each national sample was derived from the current census data of the statistical offices or, alternatively, Eurostat. Each national sample was considered representative when age, gender and social attributes of the population had the same probability of becoming part of this sample. Therefore, the confidence level of the study needs to be considered. The confidence level was set at 95%.

The structure of the sample and compliance with the confidence level was as important in the sampling procedure as the possibility of obtaining a predetermined quota structure from existing panel members. For this purpose, the social-, age- and gender-specific response rates of each country were taken into account. Quota control – pre-defining the proportions of a given age, gender, and social group in the population – was applied to ensure that the exact target and 95% confidence level were achieved.

The target group for the data collection was the general population aged 18 years and above from all states and regions in the covered countries. After cleaning and eliminating incomplete responses, we obtained data from $N = 10,391$ respondents. The final sample

Fig. 1. The main reason why respondents do not use UGS (n = 1058).

represented a complete, scaled-down mirror image of the population so that all (essential) characteristics of the population could be reproduced correctly. We use a subset of this sample limited to UGS non-users (n = 1058).

Detailed information on the structure of national samples according to the social and age distribution can be found in the [Electronic Supplementary Material Table 2](#).

2.3. Statistical analysis

We used descriptive statistics, such as relative frequencies and means to quantify the distribution of answers among respondents. In addition, to test whether the two groups (UGS users vs. non-users) differ statistically significantly from each other, we applied the Wald test for equality of proportions (Azen & Walker, 2021, pp. 25–26).

The respondents provided information on income on a scale from 1 to 15, with an assignation of income range to each of the values on the scale. To calculate the mean income level, we used the middle value of income for a given range (the [Electronic Supplementary Material Table 3](#)). Statistical analysis was conducted in IBM SPSS Statistics 27.0.

2.4. Hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis

The hierarchical agglomerative clustering algorithms (Maimon & Rokach, 2005) were applied to indicate similarities between countries in terms of the main reasons for not using UGS. The analysis enables countries to be grouped and organized according to five main reasons for not using UGS. For each reason, a variable was calculated as the share of respondents who do not go to UGS in relation to the total number of respondents who declared that they do not go to the UGS in the given country (see the [Electronic Supplementary Material Table 4](#) for details). The square Euclidean distance between these five input variables and the mean distance between clusters was calculated. The main output from the analysis is represented by a diagram that shows potential clusters in terms of the aggregated distance between countries. The shorter the distance, the higher the number of clusters and the more similar the countries which belong to such a cluster. Initially, the number of clusters was undetermined and the analysis started by assigning each country to a separate cluster (Peruta, 2018).

3. Results

3.1. Socio-economic and demographic characteristics of those who do not use UGS

The survey reveals that 10.2% (n = 1058) of all respondents do not use UGS. Those who do not use UGS differ statistically significantly from UGS users in terms of gender, age, education level, income and having children (Table 1). The shares of respondents aged 51–65 and 66+ in the total number of UGS non-users are 18% and 20%, respectively. This is higher than among UGS users, where the share of those aged between 51 and 65 is 14%, and those aged 66 and above – 13%.

When it comes to education level, 60% of all UGS non-users are highly educated (having a diploma or degree, e.g., bachelor, master, PhD), while among UGS users, this share is only 43.9%. In comparison, the share of lowly educated (no qualifications or school up to 19 years of age) is 40% among UGS non-users versus 56.1% for UGS users.

Also, we found that respondents without children in their households are less often UGS users than those with children. The percentage of UGS users among those respondents who have children is 92%, which is higher by 4p.p. than the share of UGS users among those who do not have children. The share of respondents who have children among UGS non-users is 29% while among UGS users it is much higher and equal to 39%.

3.2. Reasons why people do not use UGS among the socio-economically vulnerable groups

After the initial characterization of UGS non-users, we checked what are the reasons for not using UGS and whether the reasons differ depending on the respondents' characteristics. Fig. 1 shows that lack of time, long distance to green space, and lack of interest are the most common reasons why people do not use UGS. These reasons are reported at relatively similar proportions. In contrast, only <10% of those who do not use UGS stated that they are physically not able to get there. Between 2.7% and 3.9% of respondents reported problems such as allergies, poor accessibility, fear of wild animals and fear of getting lost. Other, not listed reasons for not using UGS were declared by 11% of non-users.

In addition, UGS non-users differ from each other rather than forming a homogenous group. We checked whether the shares of motivations for not using UGS within socio-economically disadvantaged groups (Table 2). These results inform whether a given socio-

Table 1
Socio-economic and demographic characteristics of UGS users and non-users.

Individual's features	Users	Non-users	P-value
Gender			
Female	51.0%	52.5%	0.39
Male	48.8%	46.2%	0.12
Other	0.2%	1.3%	
Age			
18–30	31.9%	26.0%	0.00***
31–50	40.8%	36.0%	0.00***
51–65	14.3%	18.3%	0.00***
66+	13.0%	19.7%	0.00***
Education level			
School up to 16 years of age	9.0%	4.2%	0.00***
School between 17 and 19 years of age	45.6%	35.2%	0.00***
Undergraduate university degree or equivalent (Bachelor)	27.4%	35.7%	0.00***
Postgraduate university diploma or degree (e.g., Master, PhD)	16.5%	24.3%	0.00***
No qualifications	1.5%	0.6%	0.00***
Income levels			
Less than EUR 3,500	9.6%	14.6%	0.00***
EUR 3,500–6,500	8.8%	9.5%	0.49
EUR 6,501–9,500	7.5%	6.9%	0.48
EUR 9,501–13,000	8.3%	7.3%	0.25
EUR 13,001–16,000	7.2%	5.3%	0.01***
EUR 16,001–22,000	9.4%	7.3%	0.02**
EUR 22,001–27,000	7.3%	5.6%	0.03**
EUR 27,001–32,000	5.3%	4.9%	0.68
EUR 32,001–37,000	4.5%	3.6%	0.16
EUR 37,001–42,000	4.1%	4.0%	0.88
EUR 42,001–53,000	5.1%	4.8%	0.70
EUR 53,001–63,000	3.9%	3.3%	0.33
EUR 63,001–74,000	2.7%	2.2%	0.32
EUR 74,001–85,000	2.0%	1.4%	0.22
More than EUR 85,000	3.7%	2.8%	0.13
Citizenship			
Native	90.0%	88.7%	0.17
Immigrant	10.0%	11.3%	
Having children in the household			
No children	61.3%	70.7%	0.00***
Children	38.7%	29.3%	
n (number of respondents)	9,333	1,058	

For users and non-users, we presented the shares of respondents in the total number of UGS users/non-users. P-value from the Wald test for differences in proportions. ** – significance < 0.05, *** – significance < 0.01.

economically disadvantaged group is over/underrepresented with regard to a given reason for not using UGS.

For instance, the reasons why UGS non-users do not use UGS differ between older people and those who have children. Older people mainly do not use UGS because of their physical inability to reach them (25% of all the respondents at age 66 and more chose this as the main reason for not using UGS). Other undescribed reasons for not using UGS were provided by 17% of older people, which is more often than other reasons for not using UGS from the predefined list.

The three most popular reasons for not using UGS among females are lack of time (21%), too high distance to the UGS from a living place (19%) and lack of physical accessibility to UGS (12%). Those who – more often than for other reasons – do not use UGS because of limited time are those who have children (34%). They more often than other socio-economically disadvantaged groups declared that they do not use UGS because the UGS around their living places are untidy (3.5% of all those who have children provided this reason). Lack of tidiness was signaled by 55% of all UGS non-users having children. In addition,

those who have children declared more often than other socio-economically disadvantaged groups allergies as the main reason for not using UGS (4.5%).

The lack of interest was signaled as the reason for not using UGS more often by the lowly educated (19%) than by females (13%), those with children (12%) or older people (18%). Among the lowly educated the dominant reasons for not using UGS were also lack of time (22%) and living too far from UGS (17%).

3.3. Cross-country variation in the share of UGS non-users

While the share of UGS non-users across the pan-European sample was around 10%, there is a large variety across the 33 countries (Fig. 2). The frequency distribution of these shares ranges from 2% in Turkey to 25% in the United Kingdom. In 13 countries, the share of non-users was higher than 10%: United Kingdom (25%), Bosnia and Herzegovina (20%), Albania (19%), France (18%), and Italy (17%). On the other extreme, following Turkey, are the Czech Republic, Portugal and Latvia – with the second lowest share (3%). Also, <5% of Ukrainian and Romanian respondents declared that they do not use UGS.

3.4. Clustering the countries based on the reasons for not using UGS

Fig. 3 shows the frequency of the reasons for not using UGS by country, while in the [Electronic Supplemental Material Table 4](#) we provided detailed data on the distribution of reasons for not using UGS across countries.

In most countries, limited time, long distances to UGS and lack of interest are dominant. For example, more than two-fifths of those who do not use UGS in Serbia, Bulgaria and Bosnia and Herzegovina stated that they do not have enough time to go there. Other countries where the main reason for not using UGS is lack of time are Albania (38%), Romania (36%), Slovakia (32%), Latvia (30%) and Portugal (30%). Except for the last one, the countries which list the highest shares of respondents who do not have time to go to the UGS belong to the Balkans.

In contrast, countries with a lack of interest being the main reason for not using UGS are Norway (36%) and Sweden (32%). These high shares contrast with two other Scandinavian countries – Denmark (22%) and Finland (7%). Other countries with a share of this reason among UGS non-users exceeding one-third are the Netherlands (33%) and Portugal (30%).

In some countries, such as Ukraine and the Czech Republic, about half of respondents who do not use UGS stated that they are physically not able to reach them. In other countries, such as the Czech Republic, Germany, Serbia and Switzerland, around one-fifth of respondents reported the inability to reach UGS by foot, public transport or bike as the most important reason for not using UGS.

Overall, although the distribution patterns of the reasons limiting the use of UGS seem to be country-specific, there are some patterns that are shared by clusters of countries.

Based on the reasons for not using UGS, we grouped the countries using the hierarchical agglomerative clustering analysis. Fig. 4 shows a dendrogram that resulted from the cluster analysis. The countries can be classified into homogenous clusters, the number of which differs depending on the distance (similarities) between countries. In addition, for each cluster of countries that can be derived with the use of the dendrogram, we checked for the dominant reasons for not using UGS and whether the distribution of socio-economically disadvantaged groups in such clusters differs from other clusters (Table 3).

The dendrogram shows that three countries – Ukraine, the Czech Republic and Switzerland – are unique when it comes to the reasons for not using UGS provided by the respondents. This is signaled by the high distance between countries necessary to link these three countries with any other cluster. Nevertheless, Ukraine and the Czech Republic seem to share some unique reasons for why people decide not to use

Table 2
The shares of motivations for not using UGS within each socio-economically disadvantaged group (n = 1058).

Reasons why people do not use UGS	Females	Older people ^a	Lowly educated ^b	Mean household income per year [in thousand euros]	Immigrants	Having children
I do not have time	21.1%	5.3%	21.9%	23.2	26.7%	33.9%
It is too far away from where I live	19.5%	15.9%	17.2%	23.3	19.2%	17.7%
I am not interested to go	13.3%	17.8%	19.2%	27.1	12.5%	11.9%
I am physically not able to get there	11.5%	25.0%	9.4%	18.8	9.2%	4.5%
I have allergies	3.6%	3.4%	4.0%	23.3	5.8%	4.5%
I cannot go to the UGS as these are not accessible by public transport, bike or on foot	4.7%	4.3%	3.2%	23.2	3.3%	2.9%
I have a fear of wild animals	3.8%	1.0%	2.4%	14.9	3.3%	3.9%
I have a fear of getting lost	3.1%	2.4%	2.4%	21.6	1.7%	2.6%
I find UGS around where I live to be untidy places	2.3%	2.4%	2.5%	15.0	3.3%	3.5%
I think it is unsafe	2.0%	1.0%	2.0%	20.7	3.3%	2.3%
I have a fear of domestic animals (e.g., dogs)	1.1%	1.4%	1.2%	22.0	2.5%	1.6%
UGS around me are lacking parking space	1.3%	1.9%	1.3%	28.9	0.8%	1.6%
I have a fear of danger related to falling trees/branches	0.7%	1.4%	1.0%	36.3	2.5%	1.6%
I fear getting unwell while being in the UGS	0.4%	0%	0.2%	21.8	0%	0%
Other reason	11.7%	16.8%	12.1%	23.3	5.8%	7.4%

^a Older people were defined as the respondents at age 66 and more.

^b The lowly educated were defined as respondents who finished school up to 16 years of age or between 17 and 19 years of age or have no qualifications.

Fig. 2. The share of respondents who stated they do not use UGS.

UGS. In these two countries, physical disability is the most frequently mentioned reason (50%). Interestingly, in the Czech Republic and Ukraine, the share of older people among UGS non-users is statistically significantly (p-value < 0.05) higher than the share of any other age group.

The countries that belong to each cluster differ when it comes to the dominant reasons for not using UGS as well as socio-economically disadvantaged groups that are statistically significantly more often

UGS non-users than others. For example, Austria, Germany, Denmark, France, United Kingdom, Croatia, Hungary, and Ireland belong to one cluster that can be described by the statistically significantly higher share of lowly educated than highly educated among UGS non-users. In these countries, respondents declared – more often than other reasons for not using UGS – excessive distance from their living place, being physically unable to reach UGS, and no parking space close to UGS.

In the cluster featuring Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, and Italy, those

Fig. 3. The most common reasons why respondents do not use UGS across countries (for the colour version of the figure, please check the electronic version of the article).

who have children appear statistically significantly more often among UGS non-users than those without children. In these countries the share of those who do not use UGS because of lack of time and living too far from UGS is statistically significantly higher than those who declared any other reason.

4. Discussion

4.1. Who and why do not use UGS?

Many authors tend to assume that the use of UGS depends on their quality, which is broadly associated with factors such as accessibility and attractiveness, combined with the most fundamental availability of those spaces (Akpınar, 2016; Dai, 2011; Roberts et al., 2018; Schipperijn et al., 2010; Stanley et al., 2022). This view neglects multiple individual and contextual factors that may be completely independent of UGS design. More comprehensive frameworks need to include personal barriers, next to the physical and institutional ones that have been considered so far (Salvia et al., 2022; Wolff et al., 2022).

With this study, we contribute to the knowledge on personal barriers and, in particular, connect the different reasons for not using UGS with those socio-economic groups that are typically listed as deprived when it

comes to UGS provision: females, older people, those with lower education levels and income, immigrants, and families with children (cf. Rigolon et al., 2018). Our large-scale comparison across 33 European countries indicates that the reasons why people do not use UGS are very individual but, some findings at least partly contradict the general tenets held so far.

Most importantly, while so far much attention has been paid to the fact that older people benefit from UGS (Stanley et al., 2022), it turns out that in this specific group, the share of non-users is particularly high. On the one hand, this confirms that planners need to continue to focus on how to make UGS available, accessible, and attractive to older people. On the other hand, this undermines a common assumption that older people represent one of the key groups using UGS and, indeed, additional efforts are required to make sure that older people do benefit from UGS. It is possible that older people simply have difficulties reaching UGS, which are cumulatively reflected in the main reasons for not using UGS they provided in our survey, such as distance to UGS, difficulties in physically reaching them, and lack of parking spaces. Interestingly, physical disability and poor health were considerably more likely to be given by older people and/or more affluent respondents as a reason that may compromise UGS visits (Boyd et al., 2018). This may explain why elderly people are less likely to use UGS.

Fig. 4. The dendrogram with the clusters of countries similar in terms of the reasons for which respondents do not use UGS.

In the same vein, it is traditionally assumed that UGS are used by families with children, and UGS are often planned to meet their needs, both in terms of their distribution (availability) and in terms of the provided amenities and facilities (attractiveness). However, while indeed the share of non-users is smaller among families with children than among those without children, almost one-third of non-users are those with children. Quite often, they indicate lack of time as the reason not to enjoy UGS (cf. [Izenstark & Ebata, 2022](#)). Another reason why those with children do not use UGS is that they see UGS around their living places as untidy. This may be related to the fact that at least some of them, especially those with many children might live in deprived areas (cf. [Boyd et al., 2018](#)). UGS in those areas might be poorly equipped and managed, which makes the families with children and lowly educated see them as untidy and so resign from using them.

What is particularly striking is that only 25% of those who do not visit UGS because of perceiving them as untidy were respondents with higher education levels. Perhaps this is because of the differences in

what is treated as a lack of tidiness by the respondents with higher and lower education levels. For example, spontaneous vegetation and abandonment of intentional cultivation could be perceived by lowly educated respondents as UGS untidiness, while highly educated respondents, with high ecological awareness, could better perceive those UGS ([Włodarczyk-Marciniak et al., 2020](#)). In line with the environmental justice literature, both of these groups (families with children and the lowly educated) are more likely than others to live in deprived areas and – if at all – tend to be provided with UGS of inferior quality ([Pérez-del-Pulgar et al., 2021](#); [Rigolon, 2016](#)).

Another striking finding is that the share of those with higher education is higher among non-users (24%) than among UGS users (16%). If the highly educated do not use UGS, it is because of lack of time (27%), lack of interest (16%) and living too far from UGS (19%). This is in line with [Mak's and Jim's \(2019\)](#) findings for Hong Kong. In particular, they showed that less educated inhabitants visit UGS more often than the highly educated. One of the potential explanations for these differences

Table 3
Characterization of clusters from the perspective of the main reasons for not using UGS and socio-economically disadvantaged groups.

Countries which belong to the given cluster	The reasons for not using UGS	Socio-economically disadvantaged groups	n
Austria, Germany, Denmark, France, United Kingdom, Croatia, Hungary and Ireland	+ It is too far away from where I live (21.0%) - I am physically not able to get there (7.1%) + I have a fear of danger related to falling trees/branches (2.0%) + UGS around me lack parking space (2.3%)	+ Lowly educated (60.1%)+ Income (28.2)	353
Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, Italy	+ I do not have time (32.5%) - I am not interested in going (9.3%) + It is too far away from where I live (26.5%) - I am physically not able to get there (3.3%)	- Older people (11.9%) + Having children (41.1%)- Income (15.7)	151
Finland, Lithuania, Slovenia, Slovakia, Turkey	- I am not interested in going (8.2%) - It is too far away from where I live (7.4%) + I am physically not able to get there (18.9%) + I have a fear of getting lost (6.6%) + I think its unsafe (4.1%)	- Income (18.2)	122
Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Latvia	+ I do not have time (39.0%) - I am not interested in going (7.3%) - It is too far away from where I live (3.7%) - I am physically not able to get there (1.2%) + I have a fear of wild animals (9.8%)	- Older people (11.0%)- Lowly educated (39.0%)- Income (9.2)	82
Estonia, Romania, Norway	+ I am not interested in going (29.8%) - It is too far away from where I live (6.0%)	-	84
Poland, Spain, Sweden, the Netherlands, Belgium, Portugal, Russia	+ I am not interested in going (28.2%) + It is too far away from where I live (25.0%) - I have allergies (1.4%) - I think it is unsafe (0%) - Other reason (7.3%)	-	220
Czech Republic, Ukraine	+ I am physically not able to get there (50.0%)	+ Older people (40.0%)- Income (7.2)	20

We reported only those reasons for not using UGS and socio-economically disadvantaged groups, the shares of which in a given cluster are statistically significantly higher (“+”) or lower (“-”) than the shares noticed in other countries (p-value < 0.05). The shares of respondents who provided a given reason

for not using UGS or belonged to a given socio-economic group in the total number of respondents in the cluster were reported in the brackets.

could be how lowly and highly educated people use their leisure time, in particular for physical activity (Droomers et al., 2001). Also, as indicated by Panter et al. (2008), highly educated people, mostly living in cities, could have better access to many sports facilities, including sports and recreation centres, in-door gyms, and swimming pools that could be used to satisfy recreational needs, while those who live in rural areas, often less educated, have worse access alternatives and so fulfil their recreational needs in UGS. Nevertheless, this contradicts some previous studies that suggested that educational attainment plays a crucial role in UGS use (da Schio et al., 2021). Another potential explanation can be that those with higher education often own private gardens. Having access to their own private garden may compensate for a lack of perceived access to other UGS (Poortinga et al., 2021).

Lack of time as the main reason for not using UGS characterized mostly those respondents who live in Eastern Europe, mainly from the Balkan countries. This could be related to the cross-country differences in the meaning and the use of time (Haller et al., 2013). Also, Eastern European societies are in general overworked and constantly under pressure to be more productive to catch up with the better-off societies, which could further limit the amount of time of leisure activities such as UGS use (Bouget et al., 2016).

In the case of the UK, the country with the largest share of non-users, our result seems to be in line with the findings of Boyd et al. (2018), who indicated that 26% of the English population did not use natural areas or used them infrequently. Another nationally representative survey for the United Kingdom, suggests that 17% of its population visits UGS less than once a month (Thurman, 2020), while in Scotland (United Kingdom), over half of the Scottish Household Survey participants declared they visit UGS less than once a week (Colley et al., 2022).

Clearly, there is a need to investigate the reasons for not using UGS in more detail and – in particular – to disambiguate the “other reasons” using open questions. Among other things, ecosystem disservices may be yet another reason for not using UGS (Conway & Yip, 2016; Lyttimäki et al., 2008). In our study, they were represented by issues such as allergies, fear of wild animals or fear of danger related to falling trees/branches, but perhaps the issues of how natural processes and functions may actually discourage people from using UGS are more complex than it has been assumed so far. Likewise, more research is necessary on how to encourage people to use UGS by addressing the different contextual factors, including not only the design of those spaces but also the participatory design procedures that increase the sense of inclusion and ownership of UGS among potential participants (Roberts et al., 2018).

Following the literature, a lack of interest is likely to be related to place attachment issues. In this sense, “the non-place-attachment” could be a powerful tool for explaining what might be masked by the lack of interest in UGS (Haase et al., 2021). Indeed, place identity and attitudes towards the environment are largely influenced by the memories, experienced events of everyday life, and symbolic meanings attached to that place (Belanche et al., 2017; Bernardo et al., 2017; Lynch, 1981). Also, “being not interested” might be related to areas of deprivation (Boyd et al., 2018). Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that factors such as noise, air pollution, the size of the park, and the quality of its infrastructure and leisure equipment may reduce interest and, therefore, the frequency of visits (Biernacka et al., 2020).

4.2. Implications for urban planning and management

Our findings have clear implications for UGS planning and research, especially in the context of environmental justice. With this study, we signalize that ensuring the existence of UGS is not enough to encourage people to use UGS. For example, older people simply may have difficulties reaching UGS, which were cumulatively reflected in the main reasons for not using UGS, such as distance to UGS, difficulties in

physically reaching them, and lack of parking spaces. Interestingly, physical disability and poor health were considerably more likely to be given by older people and/or more affluent respondents as a reason that may compromise UGS visits (Boyd et al., 2018). This may explain why elderly people are less likely to use UGS. As such, urban planners should make efforts to help people with illnesses or visual impairment to access UGS safely and in a way that stimulates interest, pleasure and social inclusion.

Our results suggest that the reasons for not using UGS reflect a variety of individual preferences towards UGS which should be taken into account in planning and managing UGS. Instead of focusing on physical barriers related to UGS design, our study highlights the need to analyse and address personal reasons for not using UGS, which also include motivational and mental factors (see also Haase et al. 2021). Our findings highlight the need to connect expert assessments of UGS provision with studies on UGS perception by the general public.

In addition, this study adds a pan-European perspective to the debate on environmental justice. We found that European countries vary both in terms of socio-economically disadvantaged groups that could be excluded from using UGS and the reasons for such an exclusion. Low income seems to be a major determinant of potential exclusion as it appears almost in all clusters of countries. Nevertheless, other societal characteristics, usually studied through the lens of environmental justice (Biernacka et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2022), such as age or educational level, might not always determine exclusions from using UGS. This is further in line with those studies that indicate that contact with natural environments is often relatively missing among groups that could benefit the most (Boyd et al., 2018; Mitchell & Popham, 2008).

4.3. Study's limitations and further research opportunities

There is a need for further, in depth analysis, specifically focused on non-users. In particular, it would be good to allow for more flexibility in providing information on the reasons for not using UGS and connecting these reasons with the respondents' opinions about specific UGS in their vicinity and general preferences regarding UGS – through open questions.

As we strived towards the highest standards in data collection, the cleaning of the data has led to validated national datasets that are smaller than expected for some countries where market research is less well developed. Further, we noticed that for some countries, specific groups have been underrepresented (particularly older people who have less experience with online surveys). We have tried to increase the samples for these countries, but this was not possible for every country involved. This can have a – rather limited – impact on the representativeness of the results for some countries.

Also, the income categories have not been adapted to the local cost of living in the respective countries, as it was difficult to find the respective income scales for some non-EU countries. In this study, we quantified respondents' mean income level without a correction for the between-countries differences in living costs. This may affect the characterization of clusters of countries from the perspective of the main reasons for not using UGS and socio-economically disadvantaged groups.

To provide deeper insights, future studies on why people do not use UGS should focus explicitly on non-users. However, what is also unknown is how many people use UGS very rarely but who do visit them from time to time and hence – in our study – were not considered non-users. Dedicated surveys are necessary to uncover the reasons for not embracing UGS-related benefits, and they should distinguish between the intensity of UGS use and define the different levels of the use–non-use scale. Obviously, studying non-users is more challenging than studying those who use UGS, who are much easier to find, at the very least in the UGS themselves (Schipperijn et al., 2010).

5. Conclusions

The aim of the present study was to extend recent literature into the reasons people give for not using UGS, based on a large representative survey data from 33 European countries. We compared the profiles of respondents who use and do not use UGS, and investigated the reasons for not using UGS across 33 countries. The results showed that 10% of respondents do not use UGS. In contrast to much of the existing literature, older adults and those with higher education levels turned out to be less likely to use UGS than younger adults and those with lower education levels. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant group of non-users, especially in certain countries. We identified seven clusters of countries which differ in terms of the main reasons for not using UGS. Three out of 33 countries (Ukraine, the Czech Republic and Switzerland) are unique when it comes to the reasons for not using UGS provided by the respondents. Personal barriers act as an equally valid argument for not using UGS as physical or institutional barriers.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2023.104866>.

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